

Rice Momilactones and Phenolics: Expression of Relevant Biosynthetic Genes in Response to UV and Chilling Stresses

Supplementary Materials:

Table S1. Expression (Ct value) of candidate housekeeping genes (eIF-4A and actin) in rice under UV and chilling stresses

Treatment	Sample	Ct value	
		eIF-4A	Actin
UV	UVC	31.35 ± 0.07	28.72 ± 0.15
	UV2	28.23 ± 0.33	29.16 ± 0.10
	UV4	28.24 ± 0.15	29.05 ± 0.17
Chilling	ChiC	27.46 ± 0.07	26.95 ± 0.25
	Chi4	31.64 ± 0.28	26.74 ± 0.28
	Chi8	29.40 ± 0.12	23.46 ± 0.16

Data express mean ± standard deviation (SD). UVC, control rice seedlings without UV treatments; UV2, UV-treated rice seedlings for 2 h per day; UV4, UV-treated rice seedlings for 4 h per day; ChiC, control rice seedlings without chilling treatments; Chi4, chill-treated rice seedlings for 4 h per day; Chi8, chill-treated rice seedlings for 8 h per day.

Figure S1. A boxplot for the Ct values of candidate housekeeping genes (eIF-4A and actin) in rice under UV and chilling conditions. The line inside the box indicates the median. The top and bottom lines of the box display the first and third quartiles, respectively. Whiskers present the minimum and maximum Ct values.